

Characteristics of Marianna compared with standard Krasnodarsky 424.

Indicator	Krasnodarsky 424	Marianna
Stem height (cm)	116.0	120.0
Preflag length (cm)	36.9	43.2
Preflag width (mm)	1.2	1.4
Central panicle length (cm)	19.8	21.0
Seeds (no.) in central panicle	104.4	131.7
1000-seed wt (8)	31.0	32.5
Av yield from a panicle (8)	2.1	2.4
Stem thickness (mm)	0.9	1.5
Yield (t/ha)	5.4	6.1

comparable to that of standard Krasnodarsky 424 (see table). It has tall, thick, nonlodging stems, and wide, erect, intensively pigmented leaves. Increased dynamics characterizes initial growth and development phases.

The egg-shaped grain is suitable for mechanized polishing and is highly resistant to breakage. □

Zhe 733, a high-yielding, blast (B1)-resistant, good quality indica rice for China

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In recent years, indica rice breeders have been incorporating multiple resistance into high-yielding varieties. We identified Zhe 733 as having good yield potential and B1 resistance rated 3 by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). Zhe 733 was a multiple cross of IR30, IR29, Fongxuan 4, and Chi-Kuai-Ai-Xuan, released in Mar 1991 as an early rice in the double-cropped Yangtze River area.

Zhe 733 had high, stable yield potential under normal fertilization. In regional trials in 1990, it yielded 6.4-7.8 t/ha (Table 1), 6-12% higher than the check Guangluai 4. Average growth duration was 112 d in Zhejiang, 2 d earlier than Guangluai 4. Approximately 55,000 ha is now planted to Zhe 733 in South China. Morphoagronomic characters are given in Table 2.

Table 1. B1 resistance and yield potentials of Zhe 733 in China, 1990.

Site	Yield (t/ha)		Resistance to B1 ^a	
	Zhe 733	Guangluai 4	Zhe 733	Guangluai 4
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	7.8	6.9	3	7
Changsha, Hunan	7.8	6.8	3	9
Nanchang, Jiangxi	6.5	5.5	1	
Fuzhou, Fujian	6.4	6.1	3	9

^aBy SES.

Table 2. Morphoagronomic characteristics of Zhe 733 at different sites in China, 1990.

Site	Growth duration (4)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)	Fertile grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)	1,000-wt (g)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	113	81	19.8	89	72	19.1	25.8
Changsha, Hunan	111	83	20.4	98	80	18.4	26.9
Nanchang, Jiangxi	112	79	19.0	84	67	20.2	25.7
Fuzhou, Fujian	111	80	19.1	90	73	18.9	25.7

Appearance, milling recovery, chemical properties, cooking and eating quality meet the China national index for high quality rice. Grain length is 6.8 mm, with a 2.8 length-breadth ratio. The grain is semitranslucent with 24.9% amylose,

10.3% protein content, low-gelatinization temperature (5.3 alkali spreading value), and medium gel consistency (60 mm). Hulling recovery is 81.9%; milling recovery, 74.1%; and head rice recovery, 52.6%. □

Response to nitrogen of new dwarf fragrant rice varieties for transplanted conditions

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Pusa Basmati 1 and Kasturi are new dwarf fragrant rice varieties released in India in 1990. Pusa Basmati 1, a semi-dwarf of medium duration (133-135 d), has a yield potential of 4 t/ha. Kasturi is semitall, of medium duration (130-135 d) with a yield potential over 4 t/ha. Both varieties have long, slender grains with strong aroma. Kasturi also has good kernel elongation. Both are suited to the irrigated ecosystem and have export potential.

We compared Pusa Basmati 1, Kasturi and another promising variety, HKR228, with local check Basmati 370 at 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha under optimum management. The soil was Aquic Hapludoll, silt loam, with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g, and 0.1% total N. The

Performance of newly released Basmati rice varieties at different N levels at Pantnagar, 1990 wet season.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha) at 14% moisture			
	N ₆₀	N ₉₀	N ₁₂₀	Mean
Pusa Basmati 1	2.8	3.1	3.2	3.0
Kasturi	3.0	3.5	3.7	3.4
HKR228	3.0	3.4	3.5	3.3
Basmati 370 (local check)	2.2	2.8	2.8	2.6
Mean	2.8	3.2	3.3	
<u>Treatment</u>	<u>LSD (0.05)</u>			
Variety	0.2			
N rate	0.5			
Variety × N interaction	ns			

experiment was laid out in split-plot design, with four replications (N rate in main plots, and varieties in subplots).

Seedlings were raised in wet nurseries (20 Jun sowing) and transplanted on 20 Jul with basal application of 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha as per normal practice. We applied urea in three splits: 1/2 basal, 1/4 at tillering, and 1/4 at 1 wk before panicle initiation.

The Basmati varieties showed no differential response to N. N response

was significant up to 90 kg N/ha (see table). The new Basmati varieties yielded significantly higher than Basmati 370. Kasturi and HKR228 produced almost similar yields (3.3-3.4 t/ha) that were significantly higher than that of Pusa Basmati 1 (3 t/ha). □

Aruna (MO 8), a high-yielding rice variety with seed dormancy and brown planthopper (BPH) resistance from Kerala, India

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Kuttanad is a unique delta region in Kerala, with 52,000 ha of riceland 0.5-2 m below sea level. Wet season rice harvest coincides with the monsoon. Rice grains often germinate within the panicle. Pests, especially BPH, are endemic because of the warm, humid climate. Many popular high-yielding varieties have neither BPH resistance nor seed dormancy.

Aruna (MO 8)—culture KAU93 derived from Jaya/Ptb 33—was released in 1990. It has red-kerneled, medium-bold grains and 1-mo seed dormancy. The short-duration (110 d) dwarf rice is also resistant to BPH.

In field trials 1983-84, Aruna (MO 8) consistently outyielded local checks (Table 1). It also showed resistance to many pests (Table 2). □

Table 1. MO 8 (Aruna) yields in Kerala, India.

Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	MO 8	Check variety ^a
Rice research station, Moncompu, 1983-84, 3 seasons	5.3	4.9
Multilocation trials, 1984 wet season	5.2	4.4
All India Coordinated trials PVT-2, 1984 wet season, 8 locations	3.4	2.9
PVT-2, 1985 dry season, 6 locations	3.8	2.5
Farm trials, 1987-89, 3 seasons	4.3	3.6

^aJyothi for research station, multilocation, and farm trials and Rasi for PVT-2.

Table 2. MO 8 reaction to pests at RRS Moncompu and in Hyderabad.^a

Variety	Score at RRS Moncompu							Score at DRR ^b , Hyderabad ^d
	Sheath blight ^c	Sheath rot ^c	Stem borer ^c	Leaf roller ^c	Gall midge ^c	BPH ^d	BPH	
KAU93	1.4	3.7	1.0	1.9	1.0	1.7	2.2	2.5
Jyothi	4.7	4.5	3.0	3.2	3.0	3.7	2.3	4.2

^a Scored by *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) on a scale of 0-9. ^b Directorate of Rice Research. ^c Field screening. ^d Seedling screening.

Zhe 8619, a promising rice with high yields and high ratooning ability in China

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Zhe 8619, a semidwarf indica variety derived from Milyang 56/4B-58 at ZAAS, is suitable for two seasons in the double-cropped area of southern China. In Zhejiang, Jiangxi, and Hubei, it performed well in 1988-90 adaptation and yield trials in early (ES) and late seasons (LS).

Average grain yield was 7.8 t/ha in

ES and 6.8 t/ha in LS. The highest yield of 11.2 t/ha was 10-15% higher than those of local check varieties. Average growth duration was 115-125 d in ES and 90-110 d in LS. In 1990, Zhe 8619 outyielded the hybrid rice check by 18.5% in ES and 4.3% in LS (Table 1).

Zhe 8619 is cold tolerant at the seedling stage and is resistant to blast and bacterial blight. No serious pests or diseases were observed in 1989-90. During the 1990 LS in Zhejiang and Jiangxi, bacterial blight attacked many rice varieties, but not Zhe 8619.

In 1990, the Zhe 8619 ratoon crop yield averaged 4 t/ha, 52% that of the main crop (7.7 t/ha). Ratoon crop duration was 56-61 d (Table 2). □

Table 1. Performance of Zhe 8619 in yield trials in Xiantao, Hubei, China, 1990.

Variety	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)	Yield components				
				Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Fertility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Plant ht (cm)
<i>Early season</i>								
Zhe 8619	116	7.7	18.5	375	128	81.2	29.7	101
Chang-You 48-2 (check)	115	6.5	-	390	117	50.3	28.9	90
<i>Late season</i>								
Zhe 8619	91	7.2	4.3	290	112	79.2	29.5	95
Wei-You 49 (check)	96	6.9	-	269	114	69.9	29.1	89

Table 2. Ratoon rice yield and characteristics of Zhe 8619 in Xiantao, Hubei, China, 1990.^a

Stubble ht (cm)	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Fertility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
15	61	72	238	83	65.3	28.6	3.9
25	58	73	254	75	77.0	29.1	4.1
30	56	65	330	77	60.6	29.5	4.3
40	56	72	259	68	79.0	29.7	4.0

^aPlot = 4 m² (2 × 2 m), 13- × 20-cm spacing.